

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

General John de Chastelain

Brigadier-General Tauno Nieminen

Andrew D Sens

Belfast Office

**Knockview Buildings, Block 1
Stormont Estate**

BELFAST BT4 3SL

Tel No: +44 2890488600

Fax No: +44 2890488601

Dublin Office

**Dublin Castle
Block M, Ship Street**

DUBLIN 2

Tel No: +353 1 4780111

Fax No: +353 1 4780600

STATEMENT

8 February 2010

On INLA Decommissioning

“The IICD can confirm that it has conducted events in which quantities of firearms, ammunition, explosives and explosive devices belonging to the INLA have been decommissioned. The events were attended by witnesses chosen by the INLA. The INLA representatives have informed us that the arms decommissioned constitute all those under the control of the INLA leadership.”

End of statement